

TELESCOPIC WORDS IN MODERN ENGLISH.

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Annotation This article discusses the features of the functioning of the lexical units of the modern English language. In the article, the author gives his vision of some word-formation neological processes and tendencies in the English language, gives an etymological description of vocabulary, and also shows not only quantitative, but also qualitative changes in the word-formation system. The article defines the role of telescoping not only as the most productive method of word formation at the present stage of the development of the word-formation system, but also as a source for the formation of new word-formation elements and models of the macrosystem of the modern English language. language.

Keywords: vocabulary, telescopic word (telescoping), sources, affix, etymology, enrichment, word formation.

Analyzing the current state of the lexical-semantic macrosystem of the English language, we immediately note its ability to update and enrich almost exclusively at the expense of its own linguistic resources through lexical and semantic derivation, that is, by creating new units or new lexical-semantic variants of existing units, new meanings. In addition, the trend towards a decrease in the proportion of borrowings among the neologisms of the English language continues to operate: receipts from other languages in recent decades have been approximately 2.0% of the total. At the same time, for a long time, the development of the English language, as is known, was largely determined by its contacts with other languages, the results of large-scale borrowings and the corresponding "qualitative" changes that covered almost all levels of the language. The English language has become so "saturated" with foreign language elements that "own" lexical units, according to the

research of linguists, make up no more than a third of the vocabulary. At the lexico-semantic level in the diachronic sense, the foreign language influence also contributed to "qualitative" changes in the English language, as a result of which new development trends were realized in the form of active innovative ways and means of vocabulary replenishment. In this aspect, means are understood, first of all, the material consequences of the formation of productive word-formation elements and models.

The objective modern situation indicates that the English language at the lexico-semantic level is characterized by the fact that it contains a significant proportion of heterogeneous formations, namely, Greco-Germanic, Greco-Roman, Romano-Germanic and other etymological hybrids. An example can be given: when, in the middle of the last century, one of the authors of the Manifesto of the Labor Party of Great Britain introduced the word meritocracy (a social system in which the most talented people occupy the highest positions) in English, linguists began to protest against this heterogeneous word. They wrote that this education has no right to exist. However, its fate turned out to be completely different: it has functioned in English for more than half a century as a single undivided designation of a more democratic social system in countries such as the United States, in contrast to systems that were previously designated in European countries by the word aristocracy (aristocracy). Note that a common attributive derivative meritocratic was created from the word meritocracy to characterize the new social system [4]

Considering the processes, mechanisms and means of creating lexical units, we emphasize that enrichment with lexical neologisms, at the present stage of the development of the English language, occurs in it almost exclusively through morphological word formation, and a significant part of the output "building" elements (root bases, affixes) at one time was borrowed from other languages. First of all, certain changes in the role, in the functional activity of word formation methods are noticeable [4].

If a few decades ago, the first places in activity were occupied by affixation and composition (compounding), but in the 21st century, according to the calculations of scientists and the author of this article, the so-called telescope (fragmentation) takes the first place, when neoplasms are formed by splicing two parts (fragments, fragments) of existing words or one complete word and part of the second, if we are talking about fragments of existing lexemes, then they, as a rule, do not coincide with real morphemes. As a result of the action of this method and mechanism, new lexical units are created, which are called telescopes. The term telescopic is an abbreviation for the phrase "telescopic wordformation" (telescopic word formation). For the first time, this terminological combination was used by foreign linguists (Adams (1973), Kubozono (1990), Kaunisto (2000), Kemmer (2003), who proceeded from the semantics of the lexeme telescope (to form like a telescope), the meaning of which is "to become shorter, or make something shorter, by sliding sections inside one another." It is this process that accurately describes the nature of the words that are formed by this method. Note that today the term "telescopic" is not generally accepted. Terms such as blending, splices, mergers, contamination, the word hybrids, etc. are used as its synonyms.

At first, telescopes were of an occasional, comic nature, however, later linguists appreciated their ability to express concepts, for the nomination of which requires several words, as a result of which a number of telescopic formations of the English language turned into international units [2]. The most famous are modem (modem), motel (motel), smog (smog), spam (spam), transistor (transistor).

Since the second half of the twentieth century, telescoping has become a productive derivational methods, and words formed in this way cease to be casual in nature [8].

The high productivity and popularity of the telescopic method has even caused the spread of such a neologism in the English language in recent years, which is actually a symbolic designation of the very way of forming such linguistic units - franken – word (Frankenstein words). This unit consists of the part of the word

Frankenstein (Frankenstein) and the designation of the concept "word" in English - word (word). If not so long ago, only nouns were created using telescopes, then at the present stage there is an "expansion" of this method to other parts of speech, as evidenced by the active creation of other parts of speech: adjectives, for example, blandiose (bland + grandiose) (incredibly polite), blurple (blue + purple), beautifect (beautiful + perfect), squoval (square + oval) verbs like computicate (computer + communicate)), stuffocate (stuff + suffocate), spave (spend + save), etc. Let us note other trends and their telescopic implementation. So, the existing abbreviations of words are often the components of telescopes. Among them are examples of such lexical units as celeb (abbreviation of the lexical unit celebrity (famous person)), with which the neologisms celebrealty (celebrity + reality) (a famous person who is a participant in a TV show), celebutante (celebrity + debutante) (a famous person who recently became famous and comes out for the first time), celebutard (celebutante + retard) (financially secure girl who cannot get married in any way), celesbian (celebrity + lesbian) (famous girls who are also lesbians), etc. ...

In modern colloquial English speech, numerous telescopisms function with the word blog (blog), which is an abbreviation for the unit weblog (web blog), for example, celebblog (celebrity + blog) (celebrity blog), sibblog (sister or sibling + blog) (sister's blog) or brother), vlog (video + blog) (video blog) [1].

Entire phrases can be used as fragments of telescopic words. Examples include aireoke (air guitar + karaoke) (an imaginary guitar played by a person singing in karaoke), scuppie (socially conscious + yuppie) (a wealthy socially responsible young person), soapedy (soap opera + comedy) (the genre of cinema, where the features of a sitcom and melodrama are combined), etc. The telescopic scuppie (socially conscious + yuppie) mentioned here (a wealthy socially responsible young man) demonstrates another modern trend of creating fusions (it was reflected mainly in colloquial speech) - the formation of "multifragment" »Telescopic words, namely - from three fragmentary elements. The last fragment can be an abbreviation that has become an acronym, that is, received the status of a

lexical unit. This shard of yuppie (young promising urban specialist), which contains the semantics of the phrase young upwardly mobile (urban) professional person (a young person who is a specialist and lives in the city). An example of a “multifragment” coalescence is the word turducken (stuffed chicken placed in a duck and then in a turkey with a cheese sauce), consisting of such fragments as turkey + duck + chicken.

The active use of the telescopic method of creating innovations has also caused such a phenomenon that can be called "secondary telescopic", that is, when in the composition of telescopic neoplasms at least one of the fragments, which acts as a fusion component, at one time also arose as a result of the contamination of two units. The neologism vog (vog - volcanic smog is a type of atmospheric pollution that occurs when sulfur and other gases and particles that are erupted by an active volcano, in the presence of sunlight, enter into a p-tion with oxygen and moisture in the atmosphere) (volcanic + smog) is an example of such a phenomenon, since the second piece of this innovation is smog, also telescopic (smoke + fog). So, the neologism splog (splog), introduces the concept of "pseudoblog", is a fusion of such units as spam (spam) + blog (blog), and both components arose by telescoping: spam (spiced (piquant) + ham (amateur)), blog (web + log) [5].

Such word-formative elements are formed as a result of the creation of a number of telescopic units with the same fragment. The first fusion just serves as a sample word, and other neoplasms become possible not so much due to the telescopic mechanism (although this mechanism underlies, at first glance, such innovations), but due to the existence of a sample, by analogy with which these neoplasms are forming. So, at one time, telescopic Nixonomics served as a model not only for "temporally limited" occasional neologisms denoting the economic policy of the first rulers of states (Reaganomics (Reaganomics is the economic policy of President Reagan and related concepts), Bushonomics (the economic policy of President Bush and corresponding concepts), (caponomics), cybernomics (cybernomics), freeconomics (free economy), mediconomics (medical economics).

As a result of such word-formation processes, a suffix element emerged - nomics to designate types of economic activity, the economic aspect of a certain sphere of human activity. The fragment -bot (robot), which was formed as a result of the creation of a whole series of units such as cobot (cobot), knowbot (program-robot for collecting information), microbot (microbot), mobot (mobile robot), nanobot (nanobot). On the way to becoming a suffix is the second conditionally highlighted element of the word vacation (-cation), as evidenced by the regular functioning in English in recent years of telescopes daycation (vacation lasting one day), haycation (weekend at the farm by invitation), naycation (abandonment of vacation), staycation (rest at home), which are splices of the full first components (day (day), hay (farm), nay (abandonment), stay (stop)) with the second part (fragment) of the token vacation [4].

It should be noted that recently it is quite common to consider the participation of abbreviations as fragments of telescopes, which means that the process of fusion occurs either simultaneously with the process of abbreviation, or precedes this process. A similar phenomenon can be illustrated by the example of the lolbertarian neoplasm (a movement to defend the right to laugh anywhere) - the merger of the abbreviation LOL (laugh out loud) (ha-ha) and the word libertarian (supporter of freedom).

We have outlined only the most obvious innovative processes and mechanisms in the word-formation system of the English language. The role of telescope is determined not only as actually the most productive way of word formation at the present stage of the development of the word-formation system, but also as a source of the formation of new word-formation elements and models. Our research on the telescopic method of word formation confirms the axiological indisputability of the proven thesis about the systemic nature of word formation, about the real interdependence between its methods and mechanisms.

Our material indicates that the formation of new word-formation elements and models is actually due to the convergent development of national varieties of the

English language in the conditions of the modern stage of scientific and technological progress. Proceeding from the fact that the lexical units formed by telescoping are semantically rich, they correspond to the principles of linguistic economy and are attractive objects of the borrowing process, which determines the spread of Anglicisms-telescopes in other languages. It can be concluded that telescopes are an integral part of the modern vocabulary of the English language. Based on the principle of their education, which consists in the addition of two (sometimes more) lexemes, they are characterized by great semantic richness. So, in order to reveal the content of the meaning of a particular telescope descriptively, it will be necessary to use a phrase or even a sentence, which gives reason to say that telescopes are characterized by high semantic and cognitive density. It is noted that the existing abbreviations of words, contaminated lexemes and suffixes, which stand out as elements of lexemes, can act as components of telescopes.

Thus, telescopes not only enrich the vocabulary with economical neologisms, but also cause derivatives to appear on their basis.

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